

The Determinant Factors for Employees to Leave (A Case Study in a Paint Chain Retailer)

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ABSTRACT: High turnover is one of the problems faced by companies, especially small and medium enterprises. PT Fakta Asia Jaya, or Fakta Retail or Fakta Group, is one of the oldest semi-modern paint chain retailers and experiences a high turnover rate, more than the average industry. The company services depended on employee knowledge and support. The higher turnover rate becomes the real problem with the cost of hiring, training, sales, and services, which might affect profitability in the long run. Many factors, such as age (generational differences), gender, length of work, marital status, job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, and organizational culture, influence employees' decision to leave the company.

This research uses qualitative methodology through an in-depth interview approach with questions about job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, and organizational culture conducts information collected. This approach was chosen to understand whether those factors significantly influence their decision. This study proposes a recommendation for the business situation and to retain the current employee, especially the millennial generation.

Based on the result of the study, it was suggested that the factors related to the employee leaving are mainly personal reasons and related to job satisfaction and compensation benefit. The other aspect emphasized by millennials is looking for career advancement and work-life balance between the family. Also, it is found that the higher risk of the job tends to look at a higher salary or to be financially incentivized; the importance of being valued and communicating in every variable makes all generations feel satisfied and fulfilled.

KEYWORDS: Award recognition, Compensation Benefits, Career Development, Job Rotation Team Building.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's retail sales are expected to grow by USD 44.13 billion with a CAGR of 4.6% (Technavio, 2022). According to Indonesia's Ministry of Investment, retail business has the potential to be a driving force for Indonesia's economy and has contributed around 50% of the GDP for the last five years (BKPM, 2022). This shows how vital traditional retail's role is from an economic point of view; it occupies a strong position in the supply chain process. The nature of the industry itself is very labor-intensive, so employment is essential in this sector (Madhani, 2021). The success of one retail depends on how human capital management. Human capital management is critical to the business's competitive advantage and outcomes, such as profit (Warden, Han, & Nzawou, 2018; Madhani, 2021).

In the retail industry, the frontline associate is essential in shaping the core competence to compete. Frontline associates are responsible for sales and how they change their perception and deliver high-quality services to get customer satisfaction (Wangheim, Evanschitzky, & Wunderlich, 2007; Madhani, 2021). An adequate employee will enhance service quality and increase consumer retention by 5% (Madhani, 2021). It also holds the necessary skills to create sales and drive traffic to the store, such as knowing a product and switching it (Madhani, 2021). Overall, all workforce in retail, starting from the manager, merchandiser, etc., holds the key to producing sales and profits as part of the chain (Madhani, 2021).

Hence, the retail workforce becomes a significant investment for a retail company. However, this industry has an 11.4% turnover rate globally, which is 1% higher than the average sector (Lewis & Soroñgon, 2022). In 2020, Indonesia had the fourth-highest turnover rate of 15.8% (Ferdian, Luturlean, Zhafira, & Izumi, 2020). This creates a consequence for an organization, especially on the cost of recruiting, training, developing, and retaining employees (Wahyuni & Ikhwan, 2022). Turnover itself can be described as an individual's thoughts about leaving the organization at some point in time shortly (Ferdian et al., 2020).

Their intention of resigning or turnover intention has interested some companies and researchers. Numerous research has been looking for the causes of their turnover, whether work-related factors, individual, or others (Cotton & Tuttle, 1986; Tian-Foreman, 2009). Work-related factors such as job satisfaction, compensation, and organizational culture have been found to have positive and negative relations to the intention (Tian-foreman, 2009). Some of their choices can be coming from their perspective. It comes from their actual behavior to end their employment based on their individual decision (Ferdian et al., 2020; Cotton and Tuttle, 1986; Tian-foreman, 2009). It becomes challenging for the HR department to understand the reason behind their intention (Arshad & Puteh, 2015).

Various research shows a link between job satisfaction and turnover intention. Job satisfaction is considered a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience. It is an individual emotional state to analyze the external and internal condition of the job towards a unique factor (Locke, 1976; Cotton and Turtle, 1986; Pandey, Singh, & Pathak, 2019). The same goes for compensation satisfaction; the sense of fair wages and benefits can be challenging for management to retain the company (Hung, Lee, & Lee, 2018; Lyons & Bandura, 2020). This satisfaction can create either positive or negative feelings toward the company (Wanger, 2007; Hung et al., 2018). Some findings show a positive correlation between salary satisfaction and the reason for the employee's intention to leave the company (Emberland & Rundmo, 2010; Hung et al., 2018).

Some research found that to retain an employee, one must build an organizational culture that can motivate them (Abdullah & Musa, 2011; Sukmasari, 2020). Strong corporate culture can influence their intention to stay or leave the company. Good organizational culture leads to behavior, commitment, and compactness to reduce their intention to leave (Robbins, 2015). Some findings also prove that employees who match the organizational culture will have a smaller turnover intention toward the company (Sukmasari, 2020).

However, some of those findings also argue that factors such as job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, and organizational culture differ from country to country. Some of the results for the retail industry in China found a negative correlation between those factors the turnover intention. Meanwhile, in India and the western context, it is a noteworthy finding regarding the correlation between those factors (Tian-Foreman, 2009; Hung et al., 2018; Pandey et al., 2019). Therefore, this paper tries to aim the understanding whether those factors have a positive correlation to turnover intention in the context of Indonesia's small and medium enterprise retail companies

2. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Pt. Fakta Jaya Asia is one of the paint chain retailers categorized as small and medium enterprises. Over the years, they have faced a 30% higher turnover rate than the average industry rate of 10%. It becomes a problem for them because their competitive advantages lie in the workforce. They are not only selling the products but also services to their customers. Therefore, losing their employee affect their daily operation, and it becomes HR's problem to do the repetitive job on the recruitment site. Therefore, this research objective is to explore further about factors whether such as individual factors of an employee, and organizational factors, such as job satisfaction, compensation, and corporate culture, are essential to influence them.

3. REVIEW OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Turnover

Turnover is defined by the number or percentage of employees leaving an organization, whether voluntarily or involuntarily. Turnover intention is to go from their position to look for another alternative job in another organization (Mahadi, Woo, Baskaran, & Yaakop, 2020). The voluntary employees deciding to leave the company is different for everyone. Meanwhile, involuntary turnover usually comes from a company terminating its employment for a specific reason (Armstrong, 2012).

However, over the years, the study of the reason behind voluntary turnover has been a severe problem for both employees and the company (Alla & RAJÂA, 2019). The rate itself is calculated by the total number of employees leaving the organization divided by the total number of employees over one year (Hausknecht, 2017). This high number of people leaving the company becomes a challenge and cost for the HR department (Alla & RAJÂA, 2019; Dess & Shaw, 2001).

HR needs to look at costs incurred when turnover occurs; these costs are grounded in human capital theory. This explains that specific human capital is acquired based on experience and training. It becomes the organization's resources to drive the performance to the competitive advantage because they are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-transferable (Shaw, 2011; Shaw, Gupta, & Delery, 2013; Yanadori & Kato, 2007; Winne, Marescaux, Sels, Beveren, & Vanormelingen, 2018). Hence Replacing this human capital requires an investment in money and time through recruitment, selection, socialization, and training. (Winne, Marescaux, Sels, Beveren, & Vanormelingen, 2018).

However, there are some arguments that turnover also positively impacts human capital. It brings a new idea that significantly challenges current practices and routines when voluntarily reducing the worst number of performances (Hancock, Allen, Bosco, McDaniel, & Pierce, 2013; Abelson & Baysinger, 1984; Wynen, Dooren, Mattijs, & Deschamps, 2018). In an optimistic scenario, it helps the stayed employee to find a fit position and competencies for the organization (Moynihan & Pandey, 2008; Steijn, 2008; Wynen, Dooren, Mattijs, & Deschamps, 2018).

However, at a certain level, turnover cannot be avoided from some employees' perspectives, such as looking for a better option. This perspective is based on an evaluation of an existing situation, such as their satisfaction with their job; the evaluation follows how the organization made them feel. Whether they have a particular attachment or not, it becomes a factor for them to make a comparison with the new job. After the comparison, they will decide whether to leave or stay (Alla & RAJĀA, 2019; Yin-Fah, Foon, Chee-Leong, & Osman, 2010; Kim & Mor-Barak, 2014).

This intention is voluntary for employees to move on from their current job because an organization cannot meet the employee's demands. Based on the planned action theory, the intention becomes more prudent when they can control the decision to leave based on the unmet need like job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, organizational culture, and individual factors (Alla & RAJĀA, 2019; Griffeth, Hom, & Gaertner, 2000; Pongoh, 2013).

b. Individual Reason (age, gender, marital status, length of services, education)

In some research, demographic variable like gender, age, and marital status is found to have a significant relation to turnover intention; event in some context is inconsistent depending on the workplace (Bajrami, et al., 2021). For instance, older employees are more satisfied in university and less likely to want to leave than younger employees (Kipkebut, 2013). The more senior employee will think carefully about their decision because the opportunity to find a new job is limited (Du Plooy & Roodt, 2013). It is different from the younger employee, who are more likely to take the risk and have the intention as part of their career advancement and exploration (Tanova & Holtom, 2008).

Especially in the millennial generation. Some studies found the challenging condition of maintaining this generation (Kessler, 2014)It becomes a loss for the company, especially with the potential employee to fill the strategic position (Fatimah, Dharmawan, Sunarti, & Affandi, 2015). Millennials have been known to stay on the job for 12 to 24 months (Yuniasanti et al., 2019; Siahaan & Gatari, 2020). The reason is that they do not view their job as necessary unless that job is meaningful for them. They look for something than money as their compensation, and it becomes a question for a company to look beyond financial compensation (NG, Schweitzer, & Lyons, 2010; Yeoman, 2014; Siahaan & Gatari, 2020). They also have certain working conditions that motivate them, such as good organizational culture, good relationships within the company, flexibility, and a dynamic work environment (Yuniasanti, Abas, & Hamzah, 2019). However, it is in a reversed role in the hotel industry, where the younger generation is likely to have lower intentions due to experience and job opportunities (Akova, Cetin, & Cifci, 2015).

Regarding educational background, some findings showed that working with a professional training degree has a lower turnover intention than one with a bachelor's degree. The one with higher education level is more likely to have higher expectations towards the employer, and it becomes more challenging to fulfill their needs (Mitchell, MacKenzie, Styve, & Gover, 2000; Choong, Tan, Keh, & Tan, 2013). Also, it shows that people with five years of working have higher turnover than those with 21 years. The greater the working length, the more likely to demonstrate a higher level of commitment than the shorter period (Lockyer & Scholarios, 2004; Watson, Taheri, Glasgow, & O'Gorman, 2017). However, this finding is based on the health worker in Vietnam, and it is different in countries like South Korea, where there is no correlation (Nguyen & Tran, 2021; Ryu, 2020)

Finally, about gender, some findings showed that females have a lower turnover rate than males. It is because female worker has lower job expectations than male workers (Chen et al., 2018). However, some studies in Malaysia and the hospitality industry have shown that women have higher turnover than male workers. Some of the reasons are that women nowadays have become more involved and demand more compensation than male workers. Some find that a male worker with marital status is likely to have a higher turnover rate. It is because they have a higher responsibility and obligation to the family. Some finding showed that married couple is expected to have a higher turnover reason for relocating, where the other spouse finds a better offer and the other will voluntarily quit and follow their spouse. Hence, there are inconsistent findings regarding gender, marital, and turnover (Chughtai & Zafar, 2006; Ahuja, Chudoba, Kacmar, Mcknight, & George, 2007; Choong et al., 2013).

c. Organization

1. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a sense or a feeling that comes from the perception that his/her job fulfills or gives a sense of fulfillment as one of the values of the job itself (Pongoh, 2013). It is perceived as how they feel about their it can be pleasant or negative based on their experiences. A finding shows that higher job satisfaction will lead to a higher commitment to the job and willingness to stay in the company. If willing to remain in the company, they will tend to contribute, be more hardworking, and perform well (Zhang, Sun, Liu, Zhou, & Zhang, 2016).

On the contrary, employees evaluate and then look for another job when they feel dissatisfied. Usually, this impulse comes from internally, irrespective of the internal and external job conditions (Ghiselli, 1974; Chhabra, 2018). Some of the studies are trying to link the dimension of job satisfaction for an employee, such as promotion/growth, relationships with coworkers and supervisor, working conditions, promotion, and advanced opportunities, security, recognition in the job, performance management system, social satisfaction company, job variety policy for banking, public sector, nurse and education industry (Gupta, 2018; Yuzuk, 1961; Nazir, 1998; Kumudha & Abraham, 2008; Khaleque & Rhaman, 1987; Ellickson & Logsdon, 2002; Masroor & Fakir, 2009; Rutherford, Boles, Hamwi, Madupalli, & Rutherford, 2009)

As for the frontline and customer-facing industry, retail training and development, career advancement and growth opportunities, relationships within the organization and co-workers, working conditions, working hours, physical work environment, and workload are essential factors for job satisfaction (Gupta, Bhaskar, & Saurabh, 2018). However, some of these findings have shown that job satisfaction becomes an essential factor for an organization to consider reducing turnover and increasing job performance (Valaei & Jiroudi, 2016; (Yucel & Bektas, 2012; Steers & Rhodes, 1978; Mobley, Griffeth, Hand, & Meglino, 1979; (Ojo)Jehnazeb & Mohanty, 2018).

2. Compensation Satisfaction

Compensation is the reward number of salaries and benefits, indirect compensation, or extra pay (Ojo, 1998). Satisfied employees will be motivated to improve their work performance, committed, and loyal to their organization (Ghazanfar, Chuanmin, Khan, & Bashir, 2011; Carraher, 2011; Vandenberghe & Tremblay, 2008; Gupta et al., 2018). The amount of compensation should be fair and reasonable, and it can be in the form of financial and non-financial. Monetary compensation consists of two forms: direct, which is wages, salaries, bonuses, and commissions; and indirect is the additional benefit other than wages, such as leave of absence, benefits, and retirement plans (Candra, Setyanti, & Wulandari, 2018). Many studies have found that higher financial compensation benefits can decrease the number of turnovers (Ghafoor, Ansari, & Moazzam, 2017; Rubel & Kee, 2015).

Non-financial rewards can be in the form of team leadership opportunities, praise, self-esteem, and recognition of achievement (Candra et al., 2018). In certain situations, non-financial rewards can be significant and a source of motivation for an employee for performance improvements. It affects employees' mental and physical well-being and work quality (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Candra et al., 2018). So, combining financial and non-financial rewards can reduce turnover intention and turnover and retain the current employee (Asiago, 2015; Candra et al., 2018; Mahadi, 2020).

3. Organizational climate or culture

Organizational culture is members' values, beliefs, and assumptions (Denison, 1996). It has five dimensions, job challenge, communication, trust, innovation, and social cohesion (Zeitz, Johanneson, & Ritchie, 1997). It affects how employees think, feel, and behave toward each other, and it enhances cooperation among the group. It dictates how they should act within the organization (Linn, 2008; Tseng, 2010; Alzubi, 2018). It can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of sharing knowledge and motivates the employee to take more initiative on the job (Worell, 2018; Haggalla, 2017).

A solid organizational culture can help employees reduce their burnout and diminish their intention to leave the company. It improves the sense of respect and enhances the employee's self-worth; it creates the feeling that this cannot be found elsewhere (Carmeli, 2005; Jha, 2009; Booth & Hamer, 2007). In some studies, a solid organizational culture can enhance job experience, and employees can take pride in their workplace (Carmeli, 2005; Deery & Shaw, 1999; Alzubi, 2018). Positive organizational culture can increase organizational commitment and minimize staff turnover (Park & Kim, 2009) Also; some findings have shown that positive corporate culture help with the company's brand image, which lead to a good reputation and retained employee (Haggalla, 2017; Hassan & Jagirani, 2019).

Based on the previous findings, some correlations influence employees' decisions regarding why they leave the company. There are four hypotheses for finding out the correlation, which are.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Based on the previous findings, some correlations influence employees' decisions regarding why they leave the company. There are five questions to uncover the factors that contribute to their choices.

- Q1. How do personal factors such as age, especially Millennials, gender, length of services, and educational background influence their decision?
- Q2. How and why does job satisfaction affect their decision to leave the company?
- Q3. How essential does' compensation benefit affecting their decision to resign?
- Q4. How does organizational culture become one factor contributing to the decision?
- Q5. How and in what ways can this company retain the employee within?

4. METHODOLOGY

Data are collected during November through a qualitative approach, face-to-face individual with a semi-structured interview. Based on findings from the previous quantitative research, there are positive and negative correlations between personal reasons, job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, and company culture to the turnover rate. This research is going to use qualitative research with phenomenological research methodology. Phenomenological research methodology approaches are often used in a single case

study. In conducting management research, this method often is used because it is easier to identify issues, show discrepancies, failures, and contrary, as well as the distinct situation in each participant (Groenewald, 2004).

This paper aims to uncover and explore the phenomenon in the company. Using qualitative research in this paper to generate, elaborate, and discloses experiences, process, and simple mechanism (Bluhm, Harman, Lee, & Mitchell, 2011). Indeed, the importance of qualitative approach is needed to address questions of prevalence, generalizability, and calibration to uncover more profound processes in individuals, teams, and organizations on how those processes unfold over time. It is also gaining a critical understanding of individual experiences and their interpretation (Lee, 1999; Bluhm et al., 2011).

As mentioned, this paper will use phenomenology as it is focused on understanding one experiences. It helps to give a direct description of one experiences as it is in the hope of transforming their experiences into something meaningful (Hayllar & Griffin, 2005). It seeks the perspective and description of the one who experienced it, what, and how. This method allows some experiences and perceptions to be brought to the surface. Also, it will allow for challenging the assumptions, policy, or practical theory (Lester, 1999).

Many approaches can be applied to this method, depending on the cases; for the single-case studies, using phenomenological approaches allows us to illustrate the discrepancies and system failure. It helps to draw attention to different situations, and fewer participants are being used. Various methods can be used while collecting the data, including interviews, conversations, participant observation, action research, focus meeting, and analysis of the personal text (Lester, 1999).

In this, studies of hermeneutic phenomenology are being used. This approach allows a researcher to interpret one experiences and phenomena to let things speak for themselves. However, some researchers argue it will contradict the findings and how things are solved subjectivity (Hayllar & Griffin, 2005).

The concern with this approach is the individual's subjective regarding situated freedom where one interpretation of the narratives provided by the participants is influenced by his/her life words and how it is interpreted. Also, for the researched subjectivity, the interpretation is not far from his/her past experiences and knowledge that helpful during the process (Neubauer, Witkop, & Varpio, 2019).

The interpretive of the hermeneutic approach starts by identifying the phenomenon that happens. The researcher investigated those experiences as they lived and simultaneously reflected on their own experiences. Researchers capture it through their writing and reflection as a cycle to develop robust and nuanced analysis. Throughout the research must maintain a strong orientation towards the study and linked between the finding as a whole. Then, provide or write the final data on how to contribute to the understanding of the whole phenomenon and enhance the meaning of the finding (Neubauer, Witkop, & Varpio, 2019)

Furthermore, to back this research, before the data collection, the general data is needed to go through the finding and interpret the data. Also, it can be used as a guideline for exposing and challenging the assumption from the previous data collected (Greening, 2019). Theories can be used to decide the research participants and develop the questions. Moreover, it helps them understand further and more profoundly the phenomena that happen (Neubauer, Witkop, & Varpio, 2019).

In general, this methodology has four steps that can be followed, starting from the bracketing by narrowing down the events that need to be investigated—followed by intuiting by examining the past study and general theory to understand the current phenomenon—also, collecting the data to meet the common understanding—then analyzing it where coding, categorizing and making sense of the situation that happens. The last critical step in this process is describing the finding with comprehension and definition of the phenomenon and putting it into verbal also written form (Greening, 2019). At last, the final part is to ensure the consistency of the interpretation of the various analysis and how each piece contributed to the total findings (Hayllar & Griffin, 2005).

In this approach, there is a need to construct a vague understanding, engage in reflection, and re-engage them with the revised knowledge. During the process, deep engagement with data via reading, writing, re-reading, and re-writing is vital to get detailed descriptions. The detailed description is categorized by qualities such as vividness, richness, accuracy, and elegance, describing the depth of engagement with the data (Neubauer, Witkop, & Varpio, 2019).

An in-depth interview is a direct and personal one where the participant is probed by an interviewer to uncover underlying motivations, beliefs, and attitudes toward specific topics. In this case, a list of questions aims to understand their feelings and reason for leaving the company.

Table 1. Research Questions

Variable 1	Personal: Name, Age, Length of services, Education
Job Satisfaction	
Variable 2	How do you feel about your current position?
	What gives you joy in this career or work?
	What makes you feel valued
	Does our company offer you adequate opportunities for you to develop yourself?
	What is success?
	What motivates you to do this job?
	Name one thing you would change in this job.
	What are your favorite things about this job? What is the responsibility?
	What causes you to feel dissatisfied on the job?
	What kind of people do you enjoy working with? Do you prefer to work in a team-based position or with individuality?
Do you feel that your job responsibilities are clearly defined?	
Compensation Satisfaction	
Variable 3	Are you familiar with the UMR?
	Do you know your compensation component?
	What are the most important factors you consider about compensation?
	Does compensation essential for you to work in a company?
	How do you determine whether you should get any raise?
	Do you satisfy with your current salary?
	Do you have any other preferences for your compensation? Such as non-financial factors, i.e., awards, recognition?
Organizational Culture	
Variable 4	Do you enjoy the corporate culture here?
	What is your ideal working environment?
	Describe your ideal employer
	How open to change are we as an organization?
	Do your managers value your feedback?
	How do you handle stress and pressure?
	What is the best part of working here?
	What makes you proud of this company?
	What is one thing you would change about the company?
	How do you guys celebrate your team's achievements?
	If there is conflict, how does your manager resolve it?
	What are your company's values?
	How would you describe the company culture?
	What personality type tends to do well here?
How do you work with old and new employees here?	
Reason To leave the company	

5. DATA ANALYSIS

An interview was conducted to understand further why employees leave the company. Five participants were asked the same open-ended questions about work situations around job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, organizational culture, and personal information. The candidate was chosen mainly from millennials and one gen x because they about to resigned from the company. As presented below is the participants' list.

Table 2. Participant Lists.

Participant	Gender	Position	Age	Length of work	Marital status	Educational background
Millennial	Male	Admin	23 Year	8.5 month	Single	College (D3)
Millennial	Male	Tinter	24 Year	2 years	Single	High School
Millennial Married	Male	Helper	24 Year	5 years	Married	Undergraduate
Gen X	Female	PA	52 Year	24 years	Married	High School
Millennial	Female	Admin	25 Year	3 years	Single	College (D3)

5.1. Job satisfaction

When it comes to job satisfaction, as mentioned in chapter two, it is a sense of feeling where a person feels enjoyed and fulfilled the pleasant feeling, so employees stay and perform. This feeling correlates with the working condition, promotion, advanced career, growth, recognition in the job, social satisfaction, and good relationship with coworkers. In general, all the participants understood the job description given to them and enjoyed their current position. As one millennial participant mentioned, *"I am doing it with enjoyable, and with additional work, I will still work on it,"* and understood that there is a job risk. Many things need to be adjusted *"... There is much pressure, and the management system needs to be adjusted"*.

They enjoy their position because the work suits their interests and abilities. They feel satisfied, and it becomes their favorite thing to do their job when they can solve their work. For instance, millennial admin participants, he/her feel happy when *"I can input the stock data, and it balances."* However, the contrast is shown in Gen X, where they feel comfortable and enjoy their work when it suits their direct supervisor *"I feel happy when my job is done and suit my boss' expectation."*

Furthermore, the job or their place has given them a growth opportunity and experience to develop themselves. As mentioned by one of the participants, their job is to do logistics and deliver the goods; he enjoys meeting with the customer in and out of the store. Also, their place gives them a chance to grow their hobby on social media to be used for work purposes. Because of that feeling, he wants to do more, as he says, *"Sometimes I want to help more for the in-house job, such as selling stuff or other departments."* It is shown that the younger generation, especially millennials, are prone to take more challenges, risks, and career advancement that give them meaning and value.

Fakta Retail also provides adequate training and chances to their employees to facilitate their interests. All the employees understood and knew there was a chance for them to go for training, career advancement, and almost equal opportunities to all chains except at the headquarters. One of the participants mentioned that in their position, the career path is not seen to grow. *"The position doesn't have any growth and comfortable. But if given a chance, I would love to have a career advancement because, with that, I can improve my skills, especially in accounting. I hope to work in several accounting-related places such as tax."* Moreover, this shows the correlation from the previous finding from Chug Thai and Zafar in 2006, who mentioned that women nowadays and their job and the challenges in which they are more involved.

The question was shifted to understanding their dissatisfaction with their current job and what they would like to change. All the participants discussed teamwork *"... when the sales counter gave a wrong phone number and can't be called, it will hinder the job."* So, when they are asked what kind of people they enjoy working with and their preferences? They all have the standard answer

that they prefer working in a team. For them, a team with a good working relationship needs good communication and being able to help each other create satisfaction in the job. *“they need to understand each other, communicate and help each other.”*

Moreover, the married millennial is talking about work-life balance because the stock checking day always happens on the 4th week of the month *“.. the busyness of checking stock on every 4th Sunday of the month makes my holiday only 3 Sundays compared to the other company. I don't have time for my family”*. It is also one thing that needs to be changed for them. While gen x straight forward talks about being appreciated on the job, *“not being appreciated.”*

Furthermore, to understand their feelings about their job and whether they are satisfied. The question is asking how they feel valued and motivated in their career. In motivation, all their answers are surrounded by the happiness of parents, family, themselves, and their needs for Gen X. So, what makes them valuable or satisfied while doing their jobs? Some millennial participants expressed their pride when they could give back to their teammates *“Because I am in this position, my friends were asking me about the current tasks.”* They felt their job becomes meaningful for them. The others felt satisfied because of being given a chance to explore and grow. *“Within five years, I can learn and master a couple of fields in the job, such as paint mixing, driver, logistics, and almost all job in the store.”* The other answer was about being appreciated and valued when working together to solve a problem.

5.2. Compensation Satisfaction

To explore further, all the participants were asked about their satisfaction with their compensations. Fakta Retail's compensation components always start from the previous year's UMR for the training months, followed by the current year, and keep adjusted with the following year or depending on employment situation or status. The last three parts are different from position to position. To begin, they were asked about their understanding of UMR, and all of them understood that they could explain *“Upah Minimum Regional, employee's minimum wages in every region.”*

The essential component is minimum wages, an allowance, bonuses, and incentives, and all the participants understood those components. Those components are being made different not only on the position based but also according to their achievement and involvement in the store. It becomes their motivation to get more; the more their team achieves the total revenue, the higher they will get their bonus and incentives. So, the following question asked whether financial compensation is essential in working. All of them were answered as necessary as their source of motivation. *“Important, as the source of motivation and become our feedback.”*

To get their point of view on the factors, they should consider getting their financial compensation. There are differences between employees with a shorter and longer working time. Also, between millennial and generation X answers. Millennial and generation x, who has worked for more than five years to 24 years, consider the length of work and loyalty to the company as the factor for financial compensation. Especially on generational x, employee performances are essential factors too. Millennials look at the job description, responsibilities, experiences, risks, and position.

So, when the question asks whether they deserve to have a raise or not and how to get it. Most of them were hesitant to answer yes—however, the answer how to get it; the majority were responded to getting more tasks and because of the length of work. As one stated, *“Yes, I deserve the raised... (why? Or how?) with additional workload and length of working ..”* Others mentioned career promotion. This shows that the longer work and the more the job, the higher their salary expectation.

Moreover, when they are asked about satisfaction with their financial compensation majority of them show their dissatisfaction. One reason mentioned is that it is not the same with the labor market *“Not satisfied because it is not suited with the labor market.”* Other is not satisfied with the additional compensation, such as incentives. *“With the basic salary is satisfied, but the incentives given are not yet ..”* one of the participants elaborated on the reason for their departure because the higher the position, the higher the risk of salary imposition. *“As I become a head of logistics as the job risk is increasing; if one of the stocks is missing or displaced, the higher the fine given to us. Meanwhile, the additional incentives or bonuses are calculated as high as other positions such as sales.”*

This becomes a significant factor for participants to resign same goes for the answer that is not suited to the labor market, where this is shown that millennials have higher expectations towards their financial compensation and are willing to take a risk to get a new opportunity looking for better offering compared to generation X. Where the answer is *“Thankful for what I have right now.”*

One of the factors because they are working longer and more comfortable with their current position, and there is a higher chance that they are not getting any more opportunities.

As they are asked whether any preferences are there to compensate them. Most of them need clarification as the non-financial compensation has never been given before in Fakta Retail, in the chain and headquarters. The questions are detailed about non-financial compensation, such as awards and recognition. All the participations agreed on the Importance of this compensation to motivate, as a form of appreciation, and have healthy competition in the chain. *"It is important to motivate others and healthy competition between retails."* Where one suggested, it can be in categories such as time discipline, the best example.

5.3. Organizational culture

Organizational culture has become one of the considerations for employees to be retained and stay in the workplace. It is a sense of values, beliefs, and assumptions created within the company. It is believed that when they enjoy the culture of their working place, it will motivate them to work more or be committed to their job. One of the factors is to understand their current state of working here with the contemporary culture; all of them agreed on one thing, which is enjoyable. One of the millennial participants mentioned, *"I am enjoying it because of the morning briefing that we start with praying. Once a week, we play games, ice breaking, and evaluation. So, the work environment is not monotonous."*

However, the differences happen with generation x, located in headquarters, that feel uncomfortable because of the teamwork. *"I am not enjoying the culture here because there is less teamwork, but it can be changed through communication between departments."* The same environment also happens; although they enjoy the working culture, communication between departments is a significant issue. *"I enjoy it, but sometimes there is a lack of communication between the sales counter and logistic team about delivery services."* Furthermore, this phenomenon also happens when they are asked about job satisfaction, where communication becomes a significant issue for them, millennials, and generation x in the working environment.

Then, when they are asked about their ideal working culture, they all have a similar answer: good communication between departments. One of the millennial participants further mentioned the working environment with more feedback from the employee and additional facilities from their direct supervisor: *"The ideal place is a table or place with partition, additional facilities like gym or exercise to support health, and feedback from my boss."* It also shows that millennials have ideal working conditions suited to their preferences. Moreover, one of the participants, a male married millennial, has higher expectations towards their financial issues with a good working environment *"The ideal working environment is comfortable for me and supported with financial stability and clear job description."*

Despite their enjoyment of working with the company, they also have their ideal working environment. Even so, they also have good experiences working with the company. One of the participants mentioned, *"I am becoming defter,"* while the other said the sense of being needed in the store *"When I had my off day, there were no people to cover the job, my boss called me to back up my other friends. There I feel needed."* The enjoyment because of their achievement *"We got the higher revenue achievement, there I felt although I am busy, my busyness has resulted."* It shows their satisfaction with the organization's culture at their current place and creates a sense of positive feeling that make self-worth where they feel appreciated, valued, and needed.

The source of enjoyment is also shown when they don't feel pressured by their leader or manager. The sense of being appreciated is revealed when their manager values their feedback and for them. It showed when they were asked whether their manager loved their feedback. All of them have mentioned the same answer, which is valued and appreciated without hesitation. Even one of the participants discussed that the opinion is not being respected *"sometimes the opinion is not being valued, we have debated it, but overall, my employer is listening."*

They describe their direct supervisor/ manager and employer; the answers differ from one to another, although most mention the ability to communicate well, observance, understanding, and care. *"My boss has taught me to work well and motivate me and keep reminding me of my tasks as well as care for their employee."* Another mentioned that their leader communicated well, leaving marks on their memory *"my leader is disciplined, observant, he/her stay silent but still observing us. A good leader understands how to make employees comfortable with their style, communicate well and relax. At the same time, we understand what they want."*

The same opinion about leadership style from different stores also felt that their direct supervisor is wise when deciding and listens to their feedback from all sides. This indicates that leadership choice and characters also play an essential part in organizational culture on how leaders behave towards their employees and can communicate well. It also shows how they perceived an ideal working environment and what they could change: communication.

For them themselves, how honest they or this company towards the change they suggested, their answer is available and unavailable with pros and cons. The difference is welcome and open in one place where the leader can communicate well and is open to their employee exploring their field. On the other hand, there are places where they accept the change even though it is hard to get because it is uncomfortable *"in my store, they are open about it but hard to accept it because it is uncomfortable. Especially about rules and regulations. It is easier to accept if there is a change of people or rotation."*

The same cons about accepting rules and regulations also happened in all chains because of the uncomfortableness created—especially for millennials who need flexibility and room to work. Also, Gen X need to be comfortable with the work environment; however, they tend to process it first instead of reacting. *"It is always pros and cons with the change. It takes a process to accept it, especially with rules and regulations."* Millennials tend to need an apparent reason for the change that happens. *"We are open to change as long as there is a clear reason and explainable."*

Sometimes, the cons will create conflict in the team, and change needs to be explained carefully by their manager/leaders. For some, respect towards their manager is shown by following their values and beliefs, which is the ability to communicate well and resolve the conflict. With their leaders' values and beliefs, they can also resolve disputes satisfactorily by communicating with their peers. For instance, with competition, they can handle it by talking it out. *"I tend to resolve my conflict by discussing the problem and how to resolve it. Then at the morning briefing, we talk it over and try to enjoy the game at the ice-breaking time."* Another way for some Generation X will still be angry at that time, then communicate it, then let it be.

One of the thick organizational cultures is seniority, as quoted to answer the question about their experiences with corporate culture. *"At my place, the tension of seniority is so strong; they feel the longer they work, the better they are, and us as a junior or newest members being ignored."* Then the following questions on how they handle it: *"I am just being polite to communicate and talk it out while with the junior, I usually talk first."* Meanwhile, Generational X, who had been working for 24 years, on their perspective they need to understand the character to understand how to communicate with them. *"Usually, I will tend to understand their character and know how to interact with them."*

At other stores, some participants will treat them as equals or peers if it is about work. *"Make a normal and fair relationship, especially about work. I do not differentiate whether they are an old or new member; communicate it well with them."* Also, other participants give the same treatment: *"I will talk it out and try to make them part of the family. I will let them know if something is wrong or if they must let me know. I will ask them for coffee or game time if it is still difficult. With my junior, I will still give the same treatment but firmer if they cannot listen."* While the other mentioned that they try to respect the oldest team and give understanding to the newest member.

Even though there is still lacking teamwork and communication, which have become an essential part of the organizational culture. The sense of social cohesion between the team member in one piece is still happening. The challenges in communication and trust are still handled well through good communication, and they still respect each other through that communication. Also, they can still celebrate their winning or achievement with a little celebration with lunch or dinner in togetherness or going for a holiday.

This celebration also can create a sense of pride and self-worth toward their hard work, that their busyness resulted in something. So, what makes them proud to work in this company? Most of the participants answered that they are valued, needed, and appreciated by their team members. Also, the enjoyable working environment. *"I am proud to work here because of the working system and comfortable environment."* The other mentioned they are proud because they work at one of the big companies in Pekanbaru. *"I am proud because this is a big company in Pekanbaru."*

The strong organizational culture that allows them to explore more contributes to a willingness to do more chores and innovate. Also, it gives them a sense of enjoyment and productivity in their work. The example, millennial who has worked for more than five years, participants can explore their hobbies to manage social media, and it becomes an innovation for their stores to be known

from social media. Also, the sense of being valued, needed, and appreciated became a strong theme for all the participants to feel satisfied with their job and working at this company even though there are still changes needed to happen in the company, such as team communication, performance system, career advancement, job rolling and imprinting the company's value to them. It is because when they are asked whether they know about the company's value, they have no clue and don't know.

5.4 Further Discussion

This research questioned a couple of factors, such as personal, job and compensation satisfaction and organizational culture, to determine whether employees leave the company. The first research question of this study is about individual factors such as age (generational), length of work, gender, marital status, and educational element becoming the determinant factors of turnover. The important reason for this variable found that females that getting married. This finding also proves that females tend to leave the company because of their marital status, which is connected to the women's duty to care for the family. However, Chung Thai and Zafar (2006) show that female has higher turnover because they have higher expectation because of their involvement in the company. This finding has shown more correlation between their reason for leaving their duty to the family and following the other spouse (Choong et al., 2003).

In contrast, the males from the younger generation and married have shown the reason for leaving the company is their responsibility to their family and looking for a better opportunity. Concerning gender and marital status, the finding has shown the consistency in male reasoning to leave the company. Align with the result from Choong et al., 2013, that Males workers with marital status have a higher turnover rate because of their responsibilities to the family. In comparison with the single male, this finding has shown that younger males with single marital status align with the discovery from Tanova and Holtom 2015, who mentioned that the more youthful generation has likely to resign to look explore more career advancement on their end.

It is aligned with the finding that the length of work has been significant in generation X with 24 years of service. In the previous study, Kipkebut (2013) mentioned that older employees are more satisfied and less likely to want to leave the company. However, the length of services or job tenure is linked to their commitment to stay in the company, especially when they feel a positive experience and needs-supply (financially) are met. It is also a prove a site-bets theory where they have accumulated certain non-material costs, such as a good relationship with their employer. As mentioned in the findings, it stimulates emotional attachment, and their commitment is higher to the company (Maden, 2014). Hence, they are working longer and have a lower turnover rate. The main reason for this is the age limit according to the law that has reached pension.

Overall, personal factors such as age with the millennial generation, gender, marital status, and length of service significantly contribute to their decision to leave the company. Meanwhile, the educational background is an insignificant finding in this research. All the participants have lower education backgrounds yet are still looking for better opportunities. Furthermore, this study found a similar result with millennial characters regarding job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, and good organizational culture (Yuniasanti, et al., 2019).

Based on the job satisfaction question thrown to the participants, communication within the team, and career development. As mentioned in the previous finding, people tend to be satisfied, especially in retail facing industry where they have training and development, career advancement and growth opportunity, relationship within the organization, working condition, hours, physical, environment, and workload (Gupta, 2018). This research has found that the more millennials are involved in their job, the more they feel satisfied and valued.

Job involvement is defined as the degree how much an employee involves in his work to the extent it influences job performance and a person's self-esteem. The higher their involvement likely it is for them to have intense experiences towards their jobs, positive or negative, as they become more sensitive to their job (Maden, 2014). However, they will tend to quit the company if their needs/desires are not aligned or not matched (Allen, Freeman, Russel, Reizenstein, & Rentz, 2001). This finding aligns with the result that all the participants are given a chance for high involvement and satisfaction with their current roles. However, their needs and desires differ from what the company has given them as compensation.

One of the significant issues with the promotion that comes along is the compensation, financially. Even though they feel satisfied with the job, if the pay growth is low, they will still leave the company (Nyberg, 2010). Participants have mentioned that the financial

compensation, especially on the incentives part, felt heavily unfairly distributed to the job responsibility taken. It is a critical influence on their decision to leave the company. This finding supported the previous study from Candra et al. (2018), Ghafoor (2017), and Rubel & Kee (2015) that shows a positive correlation between higher financial compensation benefits can decrease number or turnover.

Based on the interview, new findings are considered essential factors for employees to feed dissatisfaction with the company, which becomes another determinant factor for them to leave the company. Many of the participants have mentioned communication and cooperation amongst the team. The millennial participants have said about work-life balance and career development. The millennial finding from the previous study noted that they would likely take the risk for their career advancement (Tanova & Holtom, 2008).

As mentioned by Gupta (2018), communication takes an integral part in the organization for an employee to feel satisfied. Communication climate plays an essential role in organization integration, where all the employees receive the same information about their work at any level.

It can be horizontal or vertical, personal or group communication within the organization through informal or formal lines. This communication line affects satisfaction with the degree of the information they receive (Mustamil, Yazdi, Syeh, & Ali, 2014).

The studies from Mustamil, Yazdi, Syeh, & Ali (2014) have shown a significant correlation between communication climate and satisfaction with turnover. It is because an organization with a lack of communication activities will diminish employee performance and increase job insecurity. Communication is essential to affect cooperation within the organization and trigger affective commitment. This organizational commitment has a significant factor in how an individual behaves towards their teams and organization. In other words, communicating with this effective relationship will reduce the number of turnovers (Holzwarth, Gunnesch-Luca, Soucek, & Moser, 2021).

This study has found strong correlations between compensation benefits, work-life balance, career advancement with millennials, meaningful work experience, and nurturing work environment. This study supported the finding from Ng, Schweitzer, & Lyons (2010) that those factors are essential for millennials expected in their career. In career advancement, a millennial is looking for an organization that keeps foster on their skills development. Yet, at the same time, they still want to control their own progress. Hence, opportunities, job enrichment, ongoing training, consistent feedback, and recognition of their acknowledgment become essential (Özçelik, 2015).

Career development or advancement opportunity has a solid relationship to retaining and reducing the turnover number in some studies. It is believed that the organization gives options in the hope that employees commit because they have been provided clear direction and path for their development by their supervisor and HR department. Hence, they will stay committed to promotion and advancement and fulfill their goals and objectives (Mahadi et al., 2020). Also, with intense monitoring from their supervisor, Millennials will tend to be more engaged. A study by Ng (2010) has found that the Millennial generation considers nurture or guidance from their manager or supervisor as vital as part of their career path. Especially on the advice and constant feedback for them. One of the considerations the company can use is that they are still inexperienced with full potential, hence guidance and guiding their ambitions for their career path.

Moreover, the millennials look at the work/life balance where they can fulfill their duty as family and organization members equally. This balance is essential for the millennials to have sufficient free time as a source of welfare in the workplace. Previous research has shown that the significant reason for this factor to turnover. High work-life balance will benefit an organization. It will reduce the number of absenteeism, increase productivity, and increase retention number. It is because employees will have a higher commitment and create more quality products that lead to satisfaction for the company. Meanwhile, organizations with low work-life balance will experience common morality, higher absenteeism that leads to low productivity, and work quality that leads to higher turnover. Work demands push on higher stress levels that reduce work quality (Chemirmir, Musebe, & Nassiuma, 2018; Malik, Gomez, Ahmad, & Saif, 2010; Isnatun & Riyanto, 2020).

Nonetheless, the minor finding has shown that all participants didn't know the organization's value. Organizational value is essential in imposing a great culture. It is a commitment for an organization to commit to its statement, principle, and guidance on how they behave. It should combine with Vision, Mission, and Value. It will guide a company through constant changes environment

(Coleman, 2022). In Some findings, employees' values match the organization's values, and they will likely leave (Verquer, Beehr, & Wagner, 2003). They will have positive behavior toward their organization. It will increase their satisfaction and commitment to their job (Amos & Weathington, 2008).

To conclude, the hypothesis for job satisfaction and organizational culture has supporting contributing factors to the decision to resign from the company. Meanwhile, compensation benefits, especially incentives and pay growth, become the determinant factors for them to leave the company. However, this research has found that a couple of setback factors for Fakta Retail to retain the Millennial employee come from sub-factors from job satisfaction and organizational culture, which are communication, career development, work-life balance, and corporate value. This finding has shown new determination factors and conceptual framework for further research, as presented below.

Figure 2. New Conceptual Framework

6. CONCLUSION

Pt. Fakta Jaya Asia, or Fakta retail, has faced the same problem over the years with a high turnover rate above the industry. The research question is whether personal factors such as age, length of work, gender, marital status, and educational background become determinant factors. Based on the findings, yes, more specifically on the marital status of female millennials and the length of services for generation X. Male-specific gender, as they have a greater responsibility towards their family, also contributes to the factors. They were followed by the millennial generation looking for more significant challenges.

The second research question is whether organizational factors such as job satisfaction, compensation satisfaction, and corporate culture are essential to influence the decision to leave the company. This paper interview has shown that compensation satisfaction has a more significant influence on their decision. She followed with other factors such as communication, career development, organization value, and work-life balance that led to job satisfaction and their decision to leave the company. So, the initial hypothesis was fulfilled with the findings.

Based on those findings, there are some recommendations for PT. Fakta Jaya Asia can implement career development with more intense communication from their ordinate and HR managers to better understand employees. By allowing them to explore other positions and promotions inter-company or department through job rotation and reviewing the current compensation system and what's best for the next to increase motivation towards their job and in the hope of retaining them with the exciting package. Additional compensation is non-financial through team building to build trust with each other in the company and increase communication. After the yearly team building, there will be a ceremony through small gatherings as appreciation for them as the form that the company remembers and cares for its contribution. Last, through those activities with the employee, the hope that stakeholders involved can gain clarity to create and better version of the organization's value, vision, and mission.

Nonetheless, many areas that still need to be explored have yet to be touched. For instance, the connection between the organization culture and family business model, whether the climate affects the younger generation, such as millennials and z, attracted to work and join the company also, and whether those connections are the factors for them to resign from the company—another finding on how to retain the younger generation in the small-medium enterprise. Those findings can help many small and medium enterprises attract and retain more youthful employees and reduce the cost of repetitive jobs for their HR or admin.

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